

Can protein expression be “solved”?

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Abstract

Recombinant protein expression is central to biotechnology’s application in academic exploration as well as human health, climate applications and the bioeconomy in general. However, not all proteins can be expressed in all organisms, and the field lacks a predictive model of soluble protein overexpression that could replace laborious experimental trial-and-error. Here, we discuss the state of the field and identify the lack of large, high-fidelity datasets as the primary bottleneck to progress. We review possible assays that could be used for data collection to identify a path toward an extensible experimental platform for collecting soluble recombinant protein overexpression data across organisms. We suggest that the resulting dataset should be used to train increasingly generalizable predictive models of protein expression to answer the question: “How can predictive protein expression be solved?”

Why do we need a predictive model for protein expression?

Section summary:

This section highlights a few examples in which a predictive model of protein expression in widely-used hosts would be extremely valuable. With all of the examples, the model(s) hold the promise to save time, money and increase success of protein expression tasks.

AlphaFold has ushered in a new era in biology where predictive models complement or abrogate the need for time consuming and expensive laboratory work in protein structure elucidation. Predicting a protein structure from sequence has generated successes across the industry - from basic scientists who can now study proteins based on structural rather than sequence similarity, to companies that can take new approaches to drug design aided by accurate *in silico* structure prediction. The huge impact of AlphaFold2 has inspired a search for the next prediction task that is feasible with today's machine learning technology and equally impactful to the industry.

Soluble protein expression impacts all corners of the scientific community from the basic scientific discovery and protein engineering to biomanufacturing. Some estimate that up to 50% of protein expression attempts result in insoluble proteins¹. This statistic represents a tremendous opportunity to save significant amounts of time and money by increasing the success rate of soluble protein expression. Below, we highlight a few areas where a predictive model of protein expression would be game-changing.

Basic Scientific Research

Soluble expression of proteins is necessary in basic science research in order to probe structure, function and to develop new tools. For instance, it is incredibly valuable to know whether or not an enzyme will function when heterologously expressed in distant organisms, but to date this has required laborious and serendipitous experiments.

One illustration of this is the discovery and subsequent development of the CRISPR/Cas system. It took researchers decades after the CRISPR locus was first discovered before *S. thermophilus* CRISPR/Cas could be heterologously expressed and was functional in *E. coli*². This was a critical finding as it suggested that the system could be used in diverse species. To characterize the Cas9 enzyme, it was expressed and purified from *E. coli*, and then used in biochemical assays to interrogate its mechanism of action. Mutant versions of Cas9 were expressed to learn more about its potential uses in genome modifications by abrogating specific activities, and it

was also discovered that Cas9 could be directed to a specific site for action^{3,4}. Shortly thereafter, heterologous expression of the system was used for genome editing in mammalian cells^{5,6}. This brief history of the CRISPR/Cas system highlights how soluble protein expression in heterologous systems can be used in basic scientific research and tool development.

Just like any other protein expression project, utilization of the CRISPR/Cas system for genome modification requires tuning and troubleshooting to achieve desirable results. One example of this was the implementation of CRISPRi in mycobacteria. The canonically used Cas9 was found to be toxic when expressed, and this led the authors to explore diverse Cas9 orthologs in order to identify and implement the one with the best function and least toxicity to the host strain⁷. Soluble protein expression was a critical tool for CRISPR/Cas development from the first mechanistic insights through implementation of CRISPR as a tool in diverse hosts.

Protein engineering

Protein expression is a major bottleneck for *de novo* protein investigations. Failure to express a designed protein can make validation of the design and further study and troubleshooting difficult or impossible. Many studies have already been conducted to improve factors that impact expression of designed proteins. Examples of this include high-throughput methods for synthesizing and screening libraries of *de novo* protein domain stability^{8,9}. Other protein engineering techniques like directed evolution are similarly fundamentally limited by the need to retain intrinsic protein properties like stability, foldability and solubility, which limits the speed with which proteins can be diversified¹⁰⁻¹².

Another arm of protein engineering utilizes diverse proteins found in metagenomic samples as starting points for engineering, for example the relatively unexplored "microbial dark matter"¹³⁻¹⁵. Though sequencing and analysis technologies have improved and allowed discovery of new protein families, expression of genes from metagenomes remains a significant challenge and therefore prevents efficient exploration of this vast protein space^{16,17}.

Biomanufacturing and pharmaceuticals

Soluble protein expression in a heterologous host is an important avenue to generating enough protein for downstream investigation, or for large-scale production for industrial purposes like pharmaceuticals (insulin, herceptin, monoclonal antibodies), industrial enzymes (Carbohydrases, proteases), food proteins¹⁸, and polymeric materials¹⁹.

Though there are other avenues for generating recombinant protein, purification of soluble protein from a microbial expression system is less expensive and time consuming than

other methods^{20,21}. Recombinant proteins and protein drugs are a growing and valuable industry. For example, the recombinant protein market was globally valued at \$2.8B in 2022²¹ and revenue was over \$550M in 2021²². In these spaces, expression of soluble proteins is desired over an insoluble protein because recovery of usable protein is significantly reduced if a protein is insoluble and process efficiency is key for economic feasibility of protein production.

The first FDA approved recombinant protein therapeutic was introduced in 1982 (human insulin expressed in *E.coli*) however, today's scientists still struggle with soluble protein overexpression. Achieving industrial production-ready titers requires millions of dollars of investment along with substantial strain engineering and process development efforts²². In many instances, projects are shelved if the protein cannot be expressed at adequate titers due to issues with scaleup, and can lead to eventual abandonment of assets.

It takes a village (Soluble protein expression is a compound readout)

What is soluble protein expression?

Here, we define soluble protein expression as **measurable recombinant protein in the soluble fraction of cell lysate produced in the context of an expression system**.

Soluble protein expression is the compound outcome of numerous upstream processes (everything from DNA replication to protein folding) and is fundamentally constrained

by the biophysical characteristics of the protein (like solubility and stability, Figure 1). For this reason, protein expression is a valuable single readout that summarizes many relevant inputs.

Though proteins in aggregates or inclusion bodies may be functional, we focus our attention on soluble proteins in this review.

What factors impact soluble protein expression?

A major challenge in studying protein expression is that there are many different mechanisms by which a protein can fail to properly express (Figure 2). Broadly, the factors that impact expression can be divided into two categories^{27,28}:

1. Intrinsic factors that are driven by the specific amino acid sequence — foldability, stability and solubility — and cannot be altered without changing the identity of the protein.
2. Extrinsic factors that represent human choices in how to express the protein — host genotype, expression cassette architecture, codon choice, chaperones and foldases, media composition, lysis conditions, etc — that can be modified for better results.

Misfolded proteins also trigger stress responses that negatively feedback into host physiology, further reducing a host's ability to produce high quantities of properly folded protein.

We suggest that a dataset foundation for a predictive model must explore both *extrinsic* (different host organisms) and *intrinsic* factors (different amino acid sequences). Ideally, the impact of both intrinsic and extrinsic factors could be predicted using machine learning models that are trained on the resulting dataset.

Figure 2: Intrinsic and extrinsic factors contributing to soluble protein expression.

Where are we now, and where do we need to go?

Section summary:

- There is currently no predictive model to understand which combination of host, strain, plasmid, promoter, media, sequence etc will be most successful for soluble protein expression.
- Although there are available protein expression datasets, many are collected using different experimental methods, test expression in a single host, were not collected with machine learning applications in mind, or focus on a small subset of proteins or domains. Similarly, most existing models focus on a single variable of expression in a single host.
- The ideal dataset that would serve as a foundation for a predictive model of protein expression would be large in scale, cover diverse organisms, use consistent experimental protocols, be freely available, and be designed with machine learning (ML) utility in mind.

Current approach to soluble recombinant protein expression

Today, optimizing protein expression is an exercise in experimental trial-and-error, guided by many qualitative predictors. The first step is to choose an expression host. An in-depth review of choosing an expression system has recently been published²⁹. Three questions summarize the decision points for selecting host are²⁹:

1. Is the target protein a prokaryotic or eukaryotic protein, and does it require post translational modifications such as glycosylation?
2. Does the downstream use of the protein require post-translational modification? Does the protein have disulfide bonds? What is the size of the protein? What is the complexity (e.g. is it a membrane protein)?
3. Will higher yields or many rounds of expression be required downstream?

Once a host is selected, there are numerous reviews of strategies for improving recombinant protein expression^{20,29–32}. One must then decide on a number of extrinsic factors:

- Where to express the protein (extracellular or intracellular)
- The expression cassette details (promoter, origin of replication, plasmid background, integration site, solubility enhancing fusion proteins, tags)
- What specific expression strain to use (genetic modifications to improve expression of proteins with specific characteristics)
- What conditions to express the protein in (media, temperature, time, type of induction etc)

Today, qualitative predictors of protein expression exist and are used to improve expression, often with experimental trial and error. A quantitative ML model of protein expression based

on a large, open dataset coupled to this type of guide would enhance predictability of soluble expression and would be a widely used resource in both academia and industry.

Available protein expression datasets

Machine learning models for generalized prediction of soluble protein expression will require new, large-scale datasets that do not exist today. Existing soluble protein expression datasets are small or highly-focused, or they have been collected from proteins expressed *in vitro* rather than in living organisms. Larger datasets are typically narrow in scope (single proteins or domains) or aggregations of existing smaller datasets. They use data collected under differing conditions or protocols, and with inconsistencies in data analysis (Figure 3). This creates gaps in usable data and metadata to help build ML models³³. Finally, existing studies have typically focused on one expression host. We suggest that a valuable dataset would **use a unified experimental setup** rather than database mining, and would focus on **expression of hundreds of thousands of genes in diverse expression hosts** (for example *E. coli*, *P. pastoris*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, CHO, HEK293T etc). Building a standardized dataset of diverse proteins captured in a consistent experimental setting across various hosts of interest would be of incredible value to develop highly predictive models of protein expression.

Current protein expression models

“The biological principles for recombinant protein expression are well established; however, the ability to distinguish protein targets that express well from those that express poorly is still considered a ‘black box’ process that often requires screening many conditions to obtain a soluble product.”³⁴

Soluble protein expression is impacted by a wide variety of upstream biological processes including transcription, translation, and folding. Models today focus on making predictions of one component, such as codon usage or protein biochemical solubility, rather than making predictions of the overall process. One example of ubiquitous utilized models are those for codon optimization. When expressing a heterologous gene, it is often without a second thought that a scientist will use codon optimization to improve expression- these models have become synonymous with ordering synthetic genes for recombinant expression. Although the concept of codon optimization was first proposed nearly 40 years ago, there is little consensus between models when optimizing the same CDS for expression in the same host³⁴. Furthermore, despite substantial efforts to develop effective codon use optimization algorithms, optimized sequences continue to show differences in expression level^{34,35}. This example highlights the intricate nature of protein expression, even when focusing on a single variable like codon usage.

Most existing models related to expression focus on protein solubility. Two datasets were highlighted in Figure 3 (eSol and TargetTrack) because they were used by multiple protein solubility models as input data. The eSol data is composed of

~3200 *E. coli* proteins translated in a cell-free system (“PURE”) with and without chaperones^{36,37}. TargetTrack was a large protein expression effort driven by the Protein Structure Initiative (PSI) and was a compilation of several of their databases (PSI, TargetDB, PepcDB). This effort ended in 2017 and the data is available online to parse³⁸. TargetTrack was an enormous effort spanning 35 centers and over 100 investigators. Expression, purification and downstream structure determination of over 300,000 proteins was attempted. This was an impressive effort whose data has been used repeatedly for model building (Figure 4) though some characteristics of the dataset could be improved (for example, Hon *et al* notes, “A major limitation of this database is the low quality of its annotations... Second, the experimental protocols used for protein production and crystallization are described in free text with no internal structure, making it hard to automatically extract information about experimental conditions and expression systems for a given target.”²⁷). **We suggest that a future dataset “stand on the shoulders of giants” in order to expand the data available for model building, and to leverage learnings from previous dataset structure and collection.**

The ultimate soluble protein expression dataset

Building a generalized model of soluble protein expression across organisms will require a next-generation dataset that is larger, more comprehensive, and more extensible than the data available today. In particular, the aspects of the needed dataset that are currently missing include:

- Collect expression data on >1M unique protein open reading frames across diverse protein families.
- Express of the same proteins in several organisms to be compared side-by-side.
- Perform expression experiments *in vivo* rather than *in vitro* to capture intrinsic and extrinsic factors for expression.
- Generate “ML-ready” data and metadata that is freely available via API access and provided in a standardized and consistent experimental format(s).
- Data collection should be reproducible, shareable, scalable to enable use by scientists across fields and sectors to expand the dataset.

Figure 3: Summary of existing protein expression datasets. Citations can be found in [Supplemental Table 1](#).

Figure 4: Summary of existing solubility prediction models. Citations can be found in [Supplemental Table 2](#).

Technical Roadmap: Towards an Expression Dataset to Inform Predictive Design

Section summary:

- We suggest *E.coli* and *P. pastoris* as starting organisms for an expression dataset because these are commonly used, easy to scale microbes that would produce data useful to a wide audience (including both academia and industry). They provide a quick avenue to test the data collection platform at an economical price point.
- Depending on throughput available, singleplex methods like HiBiT, mass spectrometry and utilization of a fluorescent protein tag could be used as validation assays to spot check samples analyzed via pooled methods. These methods should be scoped as dataset collection methods, pending their scalability.
- Pooled methods like label-free proteomics and SortSeq are attractive options due to their economy, adaptability and shareability.

If the scientific community is going to invest in gathering data on soluble protein expression, how should it be done to maximize the data quality and impact? Here, we roadmap the technical options for data collection strategies. We review options for the two most critical design choices: which organisms to use as expression hosts and which assays to use to collect data. We evaluate organisms for their technical risk and possible impact, and assays for their scalability and potential for creating a robust, open dataset.

Expression Organisms

There are numerous protein expression hosts that are used due to their diverse strengths and weaknesses (For more details, see the Section: [Current approach to soluble recombinant protein expression](#)). Table 1 below summarizes some of the most commonly used microbial expression systems.

It is challenging to build a framework for prioritizing the order of data acquisition when data in every organism would be valuable. To begin, we suggest acquiring data in just two organisms that have been chosen because of their low technical risk and high impact even in isolation. Data acquisition for these two

organisms can create momentum for a much larger dataset collection effort.

Beyond the first two organisms, we suggest prioritizing the order of host expansion based on several criteria, including promoting organisms that are widely used and deprioritizing organisms that introduce new technical risks. As the dataset grows, key milestones will be expansion to other microbes, eukaryotes including mammalian cell lines and filamentous fungi, and a broader exploration of expression hosts including insect cells and cell-free methods^{47,48}. For each expression system, data collection requires identifying a specific strain genotype and expression cassette for initial data acquisition (for more details, see [Supplemental Tables 3 and 4](#)).

Data collection methods

In this section, we review methods used in gathering existing datasets, describe alternative methods, and provide an assessment of these and alternative methods for the purpose of collecting a large-scale expression dataset (Table 2).

The assays discussed are categorized as either singleplex (SPX) or pooled. SPX methods measure one sample per assay, even when multiple samples are processed in parallel or using automated systems (e.g., fluorescence readout from plates). In contrast, pooled methods combine many samples into a single measurement and require downstream deconvolution of data. Generally, pooled methods are more cost-effective and have higher throughput, while SPX methods remain simpler to implement and analyze.

Quantification of specific proteins can be done using a variety of assays, each with unique characteristics. Some commonly used assays (UV-Vis absorbance at 280nm, Bradford, BCA, Lowry) are typically used to quantify total protein, therefore the protein of interest would need to be isolated and enriched before quantification. Assays used to detect a specific protein in a complex sample include ELISA, Western-blots, SEC HPLC and mass spectrometry. Below, we review assays that have previously been utilized for high-throughput expression data collection. Reformatting the graph in Figure 4 (Summary of Existing Protein Expression Datasets) to color points by assay used, one can see that mass spectrometry, SDS-PAGE and a growth-based assays are the most common methods used in multiple large datasets (Figure 7).

Organism	Summary	Growth and culture condition	Genetics	Posttranslational modification	Expression efficiency
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Most commonly used, used in both academia and industry, easy to use, many genetic tools cheap, many strain options, not a good choice for complex proteins or those that require PTM or many disulfide bonds, easy to do HTP screening, only some strains are considered GRAS (ex Nisle 1917)	Fast and high efficiency, simple media requirement	Well-defined, simple, and high efficiency, automation friendly	No posttranslational	High without efficient secretion
<i>Pichia pastoris</i>	More recent addition to the protein expression lineup, easy to use though fewer tools than common bacterial hosts, used for complex proteins, cytokines, nanobodies, have eukaryotic PTMs, amenable to HTP screening, GRAS	"High cell density, easy scale-up"	Well-established, automation friendly manipulation	Yes but hypermannosylation can be an issue	Moderate to high of secreted proteins
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Commonly used, used in both academia and industry, easy to use, many genetic tools, cheap, many strain options, good option for secreted proteins, easy to do HTP screening, GRAS	Fast and high efficiency	Convenient for gene modification, automation friendly	Almost none	High yield with secretory expression and produces no lipopolysaccharide
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Used primarily in industry, can degrade biomass (CAZyme expression for industry), strong survivability (good for producing antibiotics, enzymes), good for secreting organic acids, proteins, enzymes and secondary metabolites. HTP screening very challenging. Strain generation and screening are not quick, GRAS	Fast and high efficiency, measurement and control of filamentous growth and macromorphology not trivial	Complex manipulation and lower transformation efficiency, automation is challenging to use	Typical eukaryotic posttranslational modifications	High efficiency secretion

Table 1: Comparison of commonly used protein expression microbes. Table 1 is adapted from Table 1 found in ³⁹ and Table 1 found in ⁴⁰. Additional citations - *E. coli* ^{22,29,41}, *P. pastoris* ^{29,42,43}, *B. subtilis* ⁴⁴, *A. niger* ^{45,46}

	Assay	Reproducible	Shareable	Scalable	Quick/easy to run and analyze	Affordable	Adaptability to other expression systems	+/-
SPX	HiBit Total = 14	✓✓ Kit-based, lysis variability	✓✓✓	✓✓ Plate-based, SPX	✓✓ Growth, lysis, kit-based reaction, readout	✓✓ Kit <\$1/sample	✓✓ HiBit tag, lysis troubleshooting	+ easy, commonly used method industrially, kit-based - cell lysis and reaction timing may require troubleshooting
	Mass spectrometry Total = 15	✓✓✓ Common method	✓✓✓	✓✓ Plate-based, MS instrument time, SPX	✓✓✓ Common methods	✓ Ni-NTA for pull downs, MS time	✓✓✓ His tag + protein extraction	+ adaptable, common "gold standard" method - costly
	Split-FP Total = 16	✓✓✓ Plate reader protocol	✓✓✓	✓✓ Plate-based, SPX	✓✓✓ Growth, readout	✓✓✓ Plate reader time	✓ FP expression, requires tuning	+ easy, commonly used - FP expression tuning
	Coomassie SDS-PAGE (+/- Ni-NTA)	✓✓ Lysis variability	✓✓✓	✗ Some steps not plate based	✓ Many steps involved	✓ Ni NTA for purification, cost of people time	✓✓✓ His tag + protein extraction	+ adaptable, common "gold standard" method - low throughput, time intensive
Pooled	Label-free proteomics Total = 12	✓✓ Newly adopted method	✓✓✓	✓✓ pool size limitation, MS time	✓? Pool size limitation, requires protocol and analysis development	✓ Ni-NTA for pull downs, MS time, pooled, depends on pool sizes	✓✓✓	+ adaptable, common "gold standard" method - low throughput, time intensive
	SortSeq Total = 13	✓✓ FACS method/ analysis	✓✓✓	✓✓✓ FACS time	✓✓ Growth, readout, FACS + sequencing	✓✓ Pooled, FACS time	✓ FP expression, tuning, FACS methods at facilities may be limiting	+ pooled, mostly adaptable - FP expression tuning; FACS method and analysis onboarding / development
	Growth based assay (DHFR) Total = 13	✓✓ Antibiotic selection	✓✓✓	✓✓✓ automatable NGS methods	✓?✓ Growth, antibiotic selection, sequencing	✓✓✓ Pooled, NGS	? Requires specific antibiotic sensitivity	+ affordable, pooled - indirect readout, adaptability unknown, uncommon assay for expression, large tag on ORF required
	Peptide flycodies	? New method and analysis pipeline	✗ method sharing prohibited	? Large pools possible, MS method time	✓? Pooled growth, new method and analysis pipeline	✓ Pooled, MS time, method dev1 cost	✓✓✓ Peptide tag on ORF and protein extractions	+ adaptable, pooled - new method with unclear chance of success, non trivial data analysis and design, not a shareable method
	Cell-Free Protease assay	? An existing method moved to a cell free system	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✗ Cell free	+ affordable and quick - not commonly used, cell-free
	YSD+FACS	✓✓ FACS method/ analysis	✓✓✓	✓✓ FACS time	✓✓ Growth, staining, readout, FACS + sequencing	✓✓ Pooled, FACS time, stain	✗ Yeast only	+ easy, commonly used - yeast specific, requires protein export to cell surface
	TAT+FACS	✓✓ Antibiotic selection	✓✓✓	✓✓✓ automatable NGS methods	✓?✓ Growth, antibiotic selection, sequencing	✓✓✓ Pooled, NGS	✗ Ecoli only	+ easy - E.coli specific, requires protein export

Table 2: Assay Assessment. Total refers to the number of check marks per row. Rows that contain red text are ruled out due to incompatibility with the defined assay characteristics.

Quantification of specific proteins can be done using a variety of assays, each with unique characteristics. Some commonly used assays (UV-Vis absorbance at 280nm, Bradford, BCA, Lowry) are typically used to quantify total protein, therefore the protein of interest would need to be isolated and enriched before quantification. Assays used to detect a specific protein in a complex sample include ELISA, Western-blots, SEC HPLC and mass spectrometry. Below, we review assays that have previously been utilized for high-throughput expression data collection. Reformating the graph in Figure 4 (Summary of Existing Protein Expression Datasets) to color points by assay used, one can see that mass spectrometry, SDS-PAGE and a growth-based assays are the most common methods used in multiple large datasets (Figure 7).

Below we describe the assays in Figure 5, listed in order of most prevalent to least (from left to right on the graph).

● Mass spectrometry

Most studies in Figure 5 that used mass spectrometry (purple points) were quantifying proteomes rather than targeted ORFs, as would be the suggested implementation for a protein expression dataset. One mass spec based method that could be implemented in a singleplex or pooled manner is label-free proteomics. This method utilizes mass spectrometry (MS) to quantify proteins either individually or in a pool (usually a proteome), without adding any label (metabolic or chemical). To run the SPX method, the protein of interest is purified by using an affinity tag (like a his-tag with Ni-NTA) and then analyzed via mass spectrometry. In a pooled scenario, the target ORFs are purified/enriched by his-tag pulldown and the pool of these proteins is analyzed via mass spectrometry. There are many

data analysis methods for label-free quantitation. For example, the Top3 method combines selective reaction monitoring (SRM) and a best-flyer approach⁴⁹ and represents a protein's abundance as the average intensity of the top 3 ionizing peptides⁵⁰.

○ Peptide barcodes (“flycodes”)

There is a recently developed peptide barcoding strategy⁵¹ in which proteins are directly barcoded with short peptide barcodes (also called “flycodes”) and then distinguished/quantified with mass spectrometry. With current techniques, there are 10,000 unique peptide flycodes that can be pooled and then distinguished using mass spectrometry.

● Growth-based assay

Growth-based assays utilize growth as a phenotypic readout for the fitness of a target protein and can be performed on arrayed (singleplex) or pooled samples. One popular version of a growth-based assay employs a split antibiotic resistance marker. This method requires reconstitution of the protein that confers antibiotic resistance, for example dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) which provides resistance to methotrexate⁵². This method is commonly used to interrogate protein-protein interactions where two proteins are each tagged with half of the antibiotic resistance marker and upon interacting, the reconstituted marker confers a fitness advantage in the face of antibiotic selection^{53–55}. Split-DHFR has been used for protein quantification in yeast to generate large datasets (Figure 7, orange points). To measure the abundance (expression) of a target protein, the target is “...expressed and fused to a DHFR (dihydrofolate reductase) fragment with the other DHFR

Figure 5: Summary of assays used to generate existing expression datasets. Reformatted Figure 3 (Summary of existing protein expression datasets) - data points are colored by the assay that was used, and ordered by the number of times the assay was used in this collection of datasets.

fragment being highly expressed. Functional DHFR is now reconstituted by random encounters and growth is proportional to the intracellular concentration of the first protein over more than 3 orders of magnitude, as validated by applying the assay to more than 2,000 yeast proteins”⁵⁵⁻⁵³. The higher the expression of the tagged ORF, the more DHFR is reconstituted (since the other half of DHFR is expressed in excess over the tagged protein and is not limiting), and therefore the more this specific strain can grow in the presence of methotrexate. When strains are arrayed, singleplex measurements can be acquired using growth curves or colony size on antibiotics to score fitness⁵³. When used in to interrogate a pool of strains, the population is sequenced before and after selection and the abundance from deep sequencing can be used to calculate fitness (growth rate), and infer expression of each variant, with up to millions of variants per pool⁵⁵.

○ HiBiT

One can measure protein abundance using a protein complementation assay (PCA) called HiBiT that utilizes a split NanoLuc luciferase. Proteins of interest are N- or C-terminally tagged with the 11 amino acid HiBiT peptide tag (a portion of NanoLuc). The HiBiT complementing LgBit polypeptide is added after cell lysis. When HiBiT and LgBit interact, they reconstitute the luminescent enzyme, NanoLuc. Luminescence intensity is proportional to the abundance of the HiBiT tagged protein of interest⁵⁶.

● SDS-PAGE

This technique is the gold standard for confirming protein expression for individually purified proteins. However, it is difficult to scale to many samples. As was mentioned previously, TargetTrack was collected across dozens of institutes. The Northeast Structural Genomics Consortium (NESG) was responsible for expressing over 25,000 constructs in *E. coli* (BL21(DE3)) from a pET based system and they utilized a SPX approach. Their first high-throughput assay for quantification had the following steps: pellet cells, lyse via sonication, purify his-tagged target proteins over Ni-NTA and then quantify via Bradford assay. They included some additional SDS-PAGE to verify their Bradford results^{57,58}. In more recent protocols, the protein purification step was removed and soluble and total cell lysate was run on SDS-PAGE⁵⁷. This was followed by staining the gels with Coomassie Blue and quantifying expression in the soluble and insoluble fractions on a scale from 0-5 based on intensity of the band observed^{57,59,60}. Capillary electrophoresis is a modern alternative to SDS-PAGE but carries high consumables cost.

● YSD + FACS (Yeast surface display + FACS)

“In yeast surface display (YSD), proteins are fused in-frame with a C-terminal epitope tag and an N-terminal Aga2p domain that localizes the fusion protein to the outer cell surface. Before successful display on the yeast surface, nascent proteins are subject to the endoplasmic reticulum quality-

control system. Misfolded proteins are marked for degradation and subsequently destroyed by proteasomes. Binding with a fluorescently conjugated anti-epitope antibody allows discrimination of variants that express on the cell surface from ones that cannot. We used fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) to collect a reference population of all yeast and the top 5% of the displaying population determined by fluorescence intensity.”⁶¹ This method is amenable to a pooled approach.

● TAT (twin-arginine translocation (Tat)-selective export of folded proteins into the bacterial periplasm)

“A protein of interest is fused in-frame with an N-terminal ssTorA Tat periplasmic export signal peptide and a C-terminal TEM-1 BLA with a deleted Sec export signal sequence (23). *Escherichia coli* expressing this fusion protein will survive in the presence of beta-lactam antibiotics if the fusion protein is present in the periplasm, because TEM-1 BLA activity is dependent on the formation of a disulfide bond. Therefore, cells producing folded soluble proteins will permit growth on ampicillin plates.”⁶¹. Similar to a growth-based assay, this method can be used on a pool of strains.

● GFP-FACS (green fluorescent protein + fluorescence-activated cell sorting)

(Wrenbeck *et al*)⁶² fused GFP to thousands of protein variants (2 proteins with thousands of mutations) to probe expression (solubility and stability, green point Figure 7). The cells were sorted by FACS and subsequent sequencing on sorted and binned populations was used to map mutations to different amounts of fluorescence. This approach allows pools of cells to be interrogated at the same time. A variation on this method is based on a PCA called Bimolecular Fluorescence Complementation (BiFC). “BiFC relies on the property of monomeric fluorescent proteins to be reconstituted from two sub-fragments upon spatial proximity (in a similar range of distance as FRET).”⁶³. The ORF of interest would be tagged with a portion of the FP (For example a portion of GFP, GFP₁₁), and the complementing fragment (GFP₁₋₁₀) would be constitutively over-expressed in the same cell. Interaction of the two fragments produces a fluorescence signal, dependent on the expression and proper folding of the ORF of interest. In a SPX setting a plate reader can be used to gather fluorescence data per strain. Extending the method to a pooled approach requires cell sorting of a population via FACS (fluorescence activated cell sorting) into bins of fluorescence as was illustrated in Wrenbeck *et al*. This is followed by sequencing of the strains present in each bin to map abundance of each strain.

● Cell-Free Protease assay

In this method, test proteins are transcribed and translated with cell-free cDNA display in a pool. The proteins are N-terminally PA tagged, and after translation they contain their cDNA at the C-terminus. These tagged proteins are then challenged with proteases, pulled down and quantified via sequencing of the C-terminal cDNA tag⁸. Recalcitrance to proteases is used as a metric for protein stability.

Comparison of assays

Characteristics of an ideal assay for large-scale protein expression dataset collection:

- Reproducible, shareable, scalable
 - **Reproducible:** Samples run three times, show the same measurement within acceptable error range. The method can be run successfully at another laboratory, and data would reproduce. This is often helped by using automation and by providing detailed and freely available protocols (shareable) and well defined and described internal standards;
 - **Shareable:** detailed assay methods (technical and analytical) are made freely available;
 - **Scalable:** the assay can be run at high-throughput and is economically feasible to do so. For SPX, throughput required is low as only control samples, and validation samples will be run using these techniques. For pooled methods, some factors that impact throughput are pool size and assay readout.

- Quick and easy
- Affordable
- Extensible to different host organisms

Reviewing the assays, we conclude that there is no clear “winner” for large dataset collection. Rather, each assay has unique pros and cons (Table 2). Some of the assays that were used to populate existing datasets (Figure 5) could be used to generate a large protein expression dataset (Mass spectrometry, HiBiT, Split-FP, growth-based assay) while others are not scalable (SDS-PAGE) or are not adaptable (cell free protease assay, YSD, TAT) or utilize methods that cannot be made publicly available (peptide flycodes). We summarize our assessment of the assays in Tables 2. More details on the assays, see [Supplemental Tables 3](#) and [4](#).

Machine learning analysis strategy

Section summary:

- Data must be collected in a manner such that the ML community can easily utilize the dataset to develop a variety of models for predicting protein expression.
- Involving ML experts throughout data collection can enable a “smarter not harder” approach that prioritizes informative, diverse new sequences rather than simply expanding dataset size with redundant or low-value datapoints.

The purpose of this review is not to prescribe machine learning models for predicting protein expression, but rather to showcase that a dataset enables such an approach.

Calculating quantitative protein abundance and storing metadata

Data would be composed of protein DNA sequence and corresponding protein abundance. Protein abundance calculations would be assay specific. Metadata would involve host, plasmid information, culturing and lysing details as well as protocol information.

Data Storage

Data should be made available in a relational database accessible to the public through a REST API (e.g., [Experiment Data Depot](#)⁶⁴ and/or other available options). Snapshots of this database at certain time points (e.g. for the initial data set, or for large data increases) will be made available to the public in a static manner through [Nature Scientific Data](#)⁶⁵, Zenodo, or similar established third party repository

Proposed ML models

A supervised ML approach could be used to predict protein concentration (response or label) from protein DNA sequence and metadata (input or features). Specifically, the prediction task takes two inputs: the DNA sequence and the desired host, and produces one output: predicted reconciled protein concentration from the SPX and pooled approaches (Figure 6).

Proposed baseline model architecture

Machine learning approaches for predicting the properties of proteins have seen significant advancements in recent years. Here, we identify promising modeling approaches by comparing soluble protein to other biological prediction tasks.

One of the closest analogies is protein structure prediction from sequence, which was revolutionized by AlphaFold2 in 2021⁶⁷.

Similar performance was later achieved using protein language models, such as ESM in 2023⁶⁸. These models are trained on large datasets of unlabeled protein sequences through unsupervised learning. Like natural language models, they tokenize proteins into short peptide snippets and challenge a model to predict the next token. This process enables the models to identify meaningful patterns in proteins that go beyond the raw sequence data, such as structural features. For instance, protein language models like UniRep can correctly classify the domain of life where the protein originated, whether a given residue is in an alpha helix or beta sheet, and has inferred the chemical similarity of the 20 amino acids⁶⁹. Today, scientists widely rely on protein language models like ESM-3 for accurate structure prediction.

Protein embeddings, derived from these language models, have been used in transfer learning to predict a variety of labeled data types, including fluorescence⁷⁰, stability⁷¹, and other biochemical properties⁷²⁻⁷⁴. This technique involves extracting the learned embeddings from a large pretrained model and using them as input to train a model on a smaller

experimental dataset⁶⁹. Protein embeddings are valuable because they encapsulate relevant features in a compressed form, which can enhance predictive accuracy and reduce the amount of labeled data required for training⁷⁵.

Currently, predicting protein properties is limited by the availability of high-quality data. Existing machine learning methods can be applied to analyze new, large datasets. We suggest using the TAPE framework⁷⁶ as a baseline for benchmarking the performance of protein transfer learning on new expression datasets. This framework could be updated with embeddings from more recent models, including ESM⁷⁷, and use SPECTRA-based train-test splits⁷⁸. After establishing baseline model performance, further research could explore new machine learning architectures that integrate additional inputs, such as codon optimization scores, Rosetta free energy predictions⁷⁹, and microbial genome embeddings⁸⁰. These inputs could provide valuable information that is not captured by protein embeddings alone, potentially enhancing predictive accuracy.

A path for platform development and vision for dataset growth

Section summary:

Though the “ultimate” expression dataset would be a tremendously challenging undertaking to generate in one combined effort, we believe that this type of dataset can be built over time.

- We need a machine-learning ready dataset containing a large number of quantitative measurements of diverse proteins. Data must be collected in a manner such that the ML community can easily utilize the dataset to develop a variety of models for predicting protein expression. It must be freely available, comparable between organisms and reproducible at different sites.
- We suggest that *E.coli* and *P. pastoris* as starting organisms for this dataset because these are commonly used, easy to scale microbes that will produce data useful to a wide audience (including both academia and industry). They would provide a quick way to test the data collection platform at an economical price point, and build momentum to expand to data collection in more hosts.
- SPX methods like HiBiT, mass spectrometry and fluorescent protein tagging will likely be cost-prohibitive for large-scale data collection. Instead, these methods should be used as a validation assay to spot check samples analyzed via pooled methods.
- Pooled methods like label-free proteomics, SortSeq and growth-based assays are attractive options due to their economy, adaptability and shareability. We believe that label-free proteomics and SortSeq would be the first assays to test since these are easier to adapt than growth-based assays.

In what dimensions could a dataset be expanded in the future?

- Different host organisms
- Waves of protein sequences (diverse proteins, deep mutation scanning of proteins, de novo proteins)
- Additional experimental conditions (temperature, media, growth vessel...)
- Changing the expression cassettes (promoters for expression, solubility tags etc.)
- Targeted localization of protein: Secreted vs intracellular expression
- Collecting different types of data that could help analyze failure modes of expression (quantifying RNA, measurement of insoluble fraction, +/- chaperones)

Conclusion

A predictive model for protein expression would be transformative for biotechnology, offering the potential to improve the efficiency of protein engineering and biomanufacturing. In this review, we have compiled the experimental and computational approaches that could make such a model possible. We recommend starting data collection in *E. coli* and *P. pastoris* as expression hosts to de-risk the methodology and build momentum for expansion to other organisms. To maximize cost-effectiveness, pooled methods should be used for large-scale data acquisition, with SPX methods reserved for validation. Machine learning researchers should be involved throughout the process to ensure that the data is ML-ready and to guide experimental design toward the most informative sequences. With the right strategy, building a predictive model of protein expression is both valuable and feasible.

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Supplement

Supplemental Table 1: Existing Dataset Citations.

Citations for main text Figure 3

Citation	Paper Title	Assay summary
82	"Quantifying <i>E. Coli</i> Proteome and Transcriptome with Single-Molecule Sensitivity in Single Cells."	Mass spectrometry
83	"Direct and Absolute Quantification of over 1800 Yeast Proteins via Selected Reaction Monitoring."	Mass spectrometry
84	"Absolute Quantification of Protein and mRNA Abundances Demonstrate Variability in Gene-Specific Translation Efficiency in Yeast."	Mass spectrometry
85	"Characterization of the <i>E. Coli</i> Proteome and Its Modifications during Growth and Ethanol Stress."	Mass spectrometry
86	"Bacterial Persistence Is an Active σ S Stress Response to Metabolic Flux Limitation."	Mass spectrometry
53	"High-Resolution Mapping of Protein Concentration Reveals Principles of Proteome Architecture and Adaptation."	in vivo method combining DHFR (abundance) and YFP (localization)
87	"Multi-Enzyme Digestion FASP and the 'Total Protein Approach'-Based Absolute Quantification of the Escherichia Coli Proteome."	Mass spectrometry
88	"The Quantitative and Condition-Dependent Escherichia Coli Proteome."	Mass spectrometry
89	"Proteome Allocations Change Linearly with the Specific Growth Rate of <i>Saccharomyces Cerevisiae</i> under Glucose Limitation."	Mass spectrometry
90	"The Cellular Economy of the <i>Saccharomyces Cerevisiae</i> Zinc Proteome."	Mass spectrometry
36	"Global Analysis of Chaperone Effects Using a Reconstituted Cell-Free Translation System."	SDS-PAGE and quantification
37	"Bimodal Protein Solubility Distribution Revealed by an Aggregation Analysis of the Entire Ensemble of Escherichia Coli Proteins."	SDS-PAGE and quantification
91	"Determinants and Regulation of Protein Turnover in Yeast."	Mass spectrometry
92	"Quantifying Absolute Protein Synthesis Rates Reveals Principles Underlying Allocation of Cellular Resources."	Ribosome profiling to estimate protein copy number
93	"Minimal, Encapsulated Proteomic-Sample Processing Applied to Copy-Number Estimation in Eukaryotic Cells."	Mass spectrometry
94	"Comprehensive Mass-Spectrometry-Based Proteome Quantification of Haploid versus Diploid Yeast."	Mass spectrometry
93	"Minimal, Encapsulated Proteomic-Sample Processing Applied to Copy-Number Estimation in Eukaryotic Cells."	Mass spectrometry
95	"Deep Indel Mutagenesis Reveals the Impact of Insertions and Deletions on Protein Stability and Function."	DHFR based assay
59	Codon influence on protein expression in <i>E. coli</i> correlates with mRNA levels	lysate SDS-PAGE
61	Trade-offs between enzyme fitness and solubility illuminated by deep mutational scanning	twin-arginine translocation (Tat)-selective export of "folded" proteins into the bacterial periplasm
61	Trade-offs between enzyme fitness and solubility illuminated by deep mutational scanning	Yeast surface display + FACS
62	An Automated Data-Driven Pipeline for Improving Heterologous Enzyme Expression	GFP-FACS
96	"The Energetic and Allosteric Landscape for KRAS Inhibition."	DHFR based assay
9	Global analysis of protein folding using massively parallel design, synthesis, and testing	Yeast surface display plus protease susceptibility + FACS
55	"Mapping the Energetic and Allosteric Landscapes of Protein Binding Domains."	DHFR based assay
97	"The Genetic Architecture of Protein Stability."	DHFR based assay
98	"From Coarse to Fine: The Absolute Escherichia Coli Proteome under Diverse Growth Conditions."	Mass spectrometry
38	Protein Structure Initiative - TargetTrack 2000-2017	Ni-NTA purification of His-tagged proteins followed by Bradford assay (and some SDS-PAGE)
99	"PaxDb 5.0: Curated Protein Quantification Data Suggests Adaptive Proteome Changes in Yeasts."	Mass spectrometry
8	"Mega-Scale Experimental Analysis of Protein Folding Stability in Biology and Design."	Protease assay

Supplemental Table 2: Existing models of expression/solubility citations.

Citations for main text Figure 4

Citation	Method	Predicted property	Expression system	Dataset Size	Dataset used	Paper Title
100	CamSol	solubility	mixed	56	Based on literature data.	The CamSol Method of Rational Design of Protein Mutants with Enhanced Solubility
101	rWH	solubility	E. coli	81	Based on literature data.	Predicting the Solubility of Recombinant Proteins in Escherichia coli
102	RPSP	solubility	E. coli	212	Based on literature data.	Prediction of Protein Solubility in Escherichia coli Using Logistic Regression
103	SOLart	solubility	cell-free	406	eSol data	SOLart: a structure-based method to predict protein solubility and aggregation
104	GATSol	solubility	cell-free	2019	eSol data	GATSol, an enhanced predictor of protein solubility through the synergy of 3D structure graph and large language modeling
105	GraphSol	solubility	cell-free	2052	eSol data	Structure-aware protein solubility prediction from sequence through graph convolutional network and predicted contact map.
106	Protein-Sol	solubility	cell-free	2395	eSol data.	Protein-Sol: a web tool for predicting protein solubility from sequence
107	ProGAN	solubility	cell-free	3148	eSol data	Progan: Protein solubility generative adversarial nets for data augmentation in dnn framework.
108	BERT	protein abundance	Saccharomyces cerevisiae	5391	compendium of 21 experimental studies "Unification of Protein Abundance Datasets Yields a Quantitative Saccharomyces cerevisiae Proteome"	The amino acid sequence determines protein abundance through its conformational stability and reduced synthesis cost
109	MPEPE	soluble protein expression	E.coli	6438	Boel et al data	MPEPE, a predictive approach to improve protein expression in <i>E. coli</i> based on deep learning
110	ESPRESSO	solubility	E. coli	8321	Based on Hirose dataset (Hirose et al., 2011). HGPD (no longer supported)	ESPRESSO: a system for estimating protein expression and solubility in protein expression systems
27	SoluProt	soluble expression	E. coli	11,436	curated TargetTrack data and NESG data. Can access training and test data	SoluProt: prediction of soluble protein expression in Escherichia coli
111	DeepSoluE	solubility	E. coli	11436	Used SoluProt filtering of TargetTrack	Prediction of protein solubility based on sequence physicochemical patterns and distributed representation information with DeepSoluE
112	SWI	solubility	E. coli	12216	PSI: Biology data. All proteins in the dataset were successfully expressed.	Solubility-Weighted Index: fast and accurate prediction of protein solubility
113	SOLpro	solubility	mixed	17408	PDB, Swiss-Prot and TargetTrack data	SOLpro: accurate sequence-based prediction of protein solubility
114	NetSolP	solubility	E. coli	18485	PSI, NESG, CamSol	NetSolP: predicting protein solubility in Escherichia coli using language models
115	ccSQL omics	soluble expression	mixed	36990	TargetTrack data.	cc SOL omics : a webserver for solubility prediction of endogenous and heterologous expression in Escherichia coli
116	DSResSol	solubility based on amino acid sequence	mixed	40,317	TargetTrack data. (training)	DSResSol: A Sequence-Based Solubility Predictor Created with Dilated Squeeze Excitation Residual Networks
117	DeepSol	soluble expression	mixed	69,420	TargetTrack data (from PROSO II paper)	DeepSol: a deep learning framework for sequence-based protein solubility prediction
118	SKADE	soluble expression	mixed	69,420	TargetTrack data (from PROSO II paper)	Insight into the protein solubility driving forces with neural attention
119	EPSOL	solubility	mixed	69,420	filtered data from PROSO II paper	EPSOL: sequence-based protein solubility prediction using multidimensional embedding
120	PaRSnIP		mixed	69,420	used data from PROSO II paper	PaRSnIP: sequence-based protein solubility prediction using gradient boosting machine
121	PROSO II	soluble expression	mixed	82299	PepcDB data (predecessor of TargetTrack) and PDB	PROSO II – a new method for protein solubility prediction

Supplemental Table 3: SPX assay details.

Assay	Tag size (a.a)	Readout	Organisms	Extensibility	Optimization	Equipment needed	Notes
HiBiT	11 HiBiT peptide tag	Luminescence proportional to quantity of protein	<i>E. coli</i> [*] <i>P. pastoris</i> [*] <i>B. subtilis</i> ¹²² HEK293T ^{123,124} Cell-Free ¹²⁵ <i>A. niger</i> ¹²⁶	Any organism that can be lysed in a manner compatible with detection reagents, including cell-free.	Cell lysis, timing of enzymatic readout, background proteins that can activate LgBit and cause signal without NanoBit	luminometer, sonicator for cell lysis	Mechanical lysis (Bead beating) followed by use of the extracellular detection kit has been cited in lactic acid bacteria ¹²⁷ and budding yeast S288c ¹²⁸ ; Used for protein transport assays in bacteria ¹²⁹⁻¹³² and for pathogen detection via phage ¹³³ however these either did not require lysis or utilize phage for cell lysis.
Mass spec	6-8 his tag	protein abundance	<i>E. coli</i> ¹³⁴ <i>P. pastoris</i> ¹³⁵ <i>B. subtilis</i> ¹³⁶ CHO ¹³⁷ HEK293T ¹³⁸ Cell-Free ^{139,140} <i>A. niger</i> ¹⁴¹	Any organism that proteins can be extracted from.	Protein extraction and instrument settings	Mass spectrometer	
Split FP assay	16 FP split	Fluorescence is proportional to the quantity of protein. Constitutive expression of another FP may be important for relative abundance (extrinsic noise)	<i>E. coli</i> ^{142,143} <i>P. pastoris</i> ¹⁴⁴ <i>B. subtilis</i> ¹⁴⁵ CHO ^{146,147} HEK293T ^{142,148} Cell-Free ^{149,150} <i>A. niger</i> ¹⁵¹	Any organism that fluorescent proteins can reliably be expressed and measured in.	expression of constitutive FP fragment, background fluorescence (growth conditions)	plate reader	Used a plate reader instead of FACS in Pichia, used flow cytometry without sorting in <i>B. subtilis</i> ,

Supplemental Table 4: Pooled assay details.

Crossed-out hosts indicate this method has not been used in that host to date.

Assay	Tag size (a.a)	Readout	Organisms	Extensibility	Optimization	Equipment needed	Notes
Tag size (a.a)	11 HiBiT peptide tag	Luminescence proportional to quantity of protein	<i>E. coli</i> ¹³⁴ <i>P. pastoris</i> ¹³⁵ <i>B. subtilis</i> ¹³⁶ HEK293T ¹³⁸ Cell-Free ¹⁴⁰ <i>A. niger</i> ¹⁴¹	Any organism that proteins can be extracted from.	Size of pools possible, strategy of pooling ORFs to maximize tryptic peptide diversity, data analysis of target ORFs, input calibration standards,	Mass spectrometer	
Readout	16 FP split	Cells sorted by fluorescence (expression) into bins, and abundance of strain/bin enumerated via NGS	<i>E. coli</i> ¹⁵²⁻¹⁵⁵ <i>B. subtilis</i> ¹⁵⁶ CHO ¹⁵⁷ HEK293T ¹⁵⁸ Cell-Free <i>A. niger</i> ¹⁵⁹	Any organism that a split-FP** can be expressed and measured in, and that FACS and downstream NGS can be performed on.	Expression of constitutive FP fragment, background fluorescence, cell sorting protocol, data analysis	FACS, sequencer	Most citations are not utilizing a split-FP for Sort-Seq. <i>A. niger</i> SortSeq utilized Flow-cytometry but not FACS.
Growth-based assay (DHFR)	81 DHFR[3] split	Following selection, abundance of each strain is enumerated via NGS and compared to the starting population.	<i>E. coli</i> ¹⁶⁰⁻¹⁶² <i>P. pastoris</i> <i>B. subtilis</i> CHO HEK293T Cell-Free <i>A. niger</i>	Any organism sensitive to trimethoprim, methotrexate or other DHFR targeting compound.	Amount of selective pressure, expression of constitutive DHFR [1,2] fragment	sequencer	For <i>E. coli</i> , other antibiotics have been used before, though not in a split-format necessarily ¹⁶³⁻¹⁶⁵ DHFR gene exists in <i>Pp</i> ^{166,167} . <i>B. subtilis</i> is known to be trimethoprim sensitive ¹⁶⁸ . In CHO cells, DHFR is used for gene amplification in DHFR null CHO cell line ¹⁵⁷ . Most literature using DHFR growth-based assay is in <i>S. cerevisiae</i> ⁵³⁻⁵⁵
Peptide flycodes	11-15 peptide barcode	Flycode abundance via mass spectrometry	<i>E. coli</i> ^{51,169} <i>P. pastoris</i> <i>B. subtilis</i> CHO HEK293T Cell-Free <i>A. niger</i>	Any organism that proteins can be extracted from.	Flycode sequences, technical method for extracting flycodes, method for running flycodes on MS, data analysis	Orbitrap mass spectrometer	

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